
Research Article

A new combination in Sri Lankan *Hopea* (Dipterocarpaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur - 342014, Rajasthan, India

Email: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

Article Details: Received: 2025-08-05 | Accepted: 2025-11-24 | Available online: 2025-11-26

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: The Critically Endangered species *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis* Kosterm. is transferred to the genus *Hopea* Roxb., following recent taxonomic treatments that recognize *Balanocarpus* as congeneric with *Hopea*. The new combination *Hopea kitulgallensis* (Kosterm.) R.Kr.Singh is formally proposed.

Keywords: *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis*, Critically Endangered, Endemic, Kitulgala, Sri Lanka

Introduction

The Asian genus *Hopea* Roxb. (Dipterocarpaceae) comprises about 115 species, distributed from southern China to tropical Asia (Singh, 2023; POWO, 2025). In Sri Lanka, the genus is represented by six species, namely *H. brevipetiolaris* (Thwaites ex Trimen) P.S.Ashton, *H. cordifolia* (Thwaites) Trimen, *H. discolor* Thwaites, *H. jucunda* Thwaites, *H. kitulgallensis* (Kosterm.) R.Kr.Singh and *H. modesta* (A.DC.) Kosterm. (Ashton, 1980; Kostermans, 1992; POWO, 2025). Except for *H. modesta*, all these species are endemic to Sri Lanka. The species *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis* Kosterm. is here transferred to *Hopea*, following the current taxonomic treatment that supports the inclusion of *Balanocarpus* Bedd. within *Hopea* (Ashton, 1980, 2003; Singh, 2023). Accordingly, the new combination *H. kitulgallensis* (Kosterm.) R.Kr.Singh is proposed here.

New combination

Hopea kitulgallensis (Kosterm.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis* Kosterm., Bull. Mus. Natl. Hist. Nat., B, Adansonia Sér. 4, 3(2): 177. 1981.

Figure 1: Holotype of *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis* Kosterm. (L0011509, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

Figure 2: Isotype of *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis* Kosterm. (BR000006991517, © Herbarium of National Botanic Garden of Belgium)

Figure 3: Isotype of *Balanocarpus kitulgallensis* Kosterm. (LE00015238, © Herbarium of the Komarov Botanical Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences)

Holotype: Sri Lanka, Sabaragamuwa province, Kegalle district, Kitulgala (Kitulgalle), across Kelani (Kelaniya) river, near flat rock bottomed tributary of Kelani river, 400 m, 4 May 1980, A.J.G.H.

Kostermans 28385 (L0011509!, Figure 1); isotypes BISH1001273!, BR0000006991517! (Figure 2), LE00015238! (Figure 3).

Paratypes: Sri Lanka, Sabaragamuwa province, Kegalle district, Kitulgala, across Kelani river, opposite rest house, stony tributary, 150 m, 28 May 1980, A.J.G.H. *Kostermans 28485* (BR0000030449459!, L0375428!, P02428127!, PH00814784!).

Distribution: Endemic to Kegalle district, Sabaragamuwa province, Sri Lanka.

Notes: This species was recently assessed as Critically Endangered under criteria B1ab(iii) + 2ab(iii); D (<https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2024-1.RLTS.T190901A220448020.en>).

Acknowledgments

The author is thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities. I am also grateful to the curators of BISH, BR, L, LE, P and PH for the images and information of type specimens.

References

- Ashton, P.S. (1980). Dipterocarpaceae. In: Dassanayake, M.D. and Fosberg, F.R. (eds.) Revised Handbook to the Flora of Ceylon, Vol. 1: 364–423. Amerind Publishing Company, New Delhi.
- Ashton, P.S. (2003). Dipterocarpaceae. In: Kubitzki, K. and Bayer, C. (eds.) Flowering Plants. Dicotyledons. The Families and Genera of Vascular Plants, Vol. 5: 182–197. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Kostermans, A.J.G.H. (1992). A Handbook of the Dipterocarpaceae of Sri Lanka. Wildlife Heritage Trust of Sri Lanka, Colombo.
- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available at: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 30 July 2025).
- Singh, R.K. (2023). A checklist of Indian *Hopea* (Dipterocarpaceae) with one new combination and lectotypifications. *Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation* 7(3): 26–40.